

Sample event data on ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) collected by Biological Station Wijster (BSW) in the years 1959, 1961, 1963, 1965, and 1966

Gijs M. Gerrits^{‡,§}, Roel van Klink^{¶,¶,¶}

[‡] Wageningen University & Research, Department of Mathematical and Statistical Methods (Biometris), Wageningen, Netherlands

[§] Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Evolutionary Ecology Group, Leiden, Netherlands

[|] German Centre for Integrative Biodiversity Research (iDiv), Leipzig, Germany

[¶] Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Department of Computer Science, Halle, Germany

[#] WBBS Foundation, Loon, Netherlands

Corresponding author: Gijs M. Gerrits (geiger-1@hotmail.com)

Abstract

Background

Historical data on invertebrates are rare and their preservation and FAIR publication is of high importance. Systematically collected historical data can greatly improve the baselines against which trends in biodiversity of these groups is measured. Therefore, we started a data publication project to digitise and publish one of the longest running insect monitoring schemes in the world.

New information

The raw data presented in the dataset have not been published before. It consists of 45.486 records of 90.070 specimens from 135 species of ground beetles caught in the province of Drenthe, The Netherlands. All specimens were identified to species level by taxonomic specialists. The data were collected using a standardised field study set-up with pitfall traps. Extensive cross-checking during digitisation guaranteed an error rate of <0.1%.

The dataset presented here forms part of a much larger dataset of 300.000 records and close to 1 million individuals of 172 ground beetles collected in the same area from 1959 to the present day, which will be further digitised in the coming years. The database has

been registered in the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF) and can be found under: <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/776f3477-2a0d-407d-8332-5bd6b1a31b4a>

Keywords

Stichting WBBS, Biological Station Wijster, historical biodiversity data, pitfall trap, arthropods, insect decline, Dwingelderveld, Mantingerbos

Introduction

Historical biodiversity data on insects and other invertebrates is rare and often consists of assorted museum specimens. Therefore, publication of historical data on invertebrates collected during standardised field studies is of high importance, as it can increase our understanding of population and community dynamics in these groups. This is particularly important considering the recently observed declines in insect abundance and diversity (van Klink et al. 2020 van Klink et al. 2023 Hallmann et al. 2019), which has received significant attention from both researchers and the public. Systematically collected historical data over long timescales can greatly improve the baselines against which trends in species diversity are measured.

Therefore, we started a project to (1) bring together, (2) digitise, (3) cross-check and (4) publish a large dataset containing close to 1 million specimens belonging to the family of ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae). The source data consist of a paper archive, lab journals, electronic files in several formats and dry and wet collection material. The data have been collected over the course of 65 years (1959 - present) in the northern province of Drenthe in the Netherlands. Beetles (and other ground-dwelling invertebrates) were collected using large metal pitfalls, dug in flush with the soil surface (Den Boer 1977). Sampling still continues with the same set-up at a selection of locations, making it, to the best of our knowledge, the longest running standardised monitoring program for terrestrial insects in the world. Fig. 1 gives an impression of the field set-up and the archive at Naturalis Biodiversity Center.

The monitoring program of Biological Station Wijster (BSW), then part of Landbouwhogeschool Wageningen, was started to study population dynamics, using ground beetles as a study system (Den Boer 1977). Some of the primary aims were to test paradigms of population regulation and stabilization (Den Boer and Reddingius 1996) and the importance of dispersal. The research was conducted in various nature reserves in Drenthe province, where sites were specifically chosen to represent 'stable' and 'unstable' habitats. The focus of the first sampling sites lay on heathlands, forests and bogs. The studied landscape had already become extremely fragmented by agricultural expansion, providing an opportunity to test the probability of extinction of species with differing dispersal capacities Den Boer 1979

In this datapaper, we present the data of all species caught in a representative selection of years from the first decade of sampling. The goal was to create a stand-alone dataset following rigorous data checking methods, after which the data would be converted to comply with the Darwin core standard in order to make it publicly available following FAIR data principles. This first dataset provides the groundwork for digitising the rest of the archive Fig. 2.

Project description

Title: Digitisation and publication of the BSW standard trapping program

Personnel: Projectgroup Wijster-data:

- Roel van Klink, German Center for Integrative Biodiversity Research Halle-Jena_Leipzig (iDiv), Martin-Luther University Halle-Wittenberg, Stichting Willem Beijerinck Biologisch Station (WBBS Foundation)
- Gijs M. Gerrits, Wageningen University & Research, Naturalis Biodiversity Center

Design description: The project entails the digitisation and cross-checking of the first part of the BSW archive (Fig. 2).

Funding: The project "Pilotproject voor het ontsluiten van data uit het langlopende Wijster loopkeveronderzoek" was funded by NLBIF grant nlbif2023.008

Sampling methods

Sampling description: Ground beetles (Coleoptera, Carabidae) were sampled year-round in square metal pitfall traps with a perimeter of 1 m. The traps were custom made, based on an earlier design used in the Meijendel coastal dunes (Gerrits and Hemerik 2022Den Boer 1977). The traps consisted of an outer trap and an inner trap, the latter of which could be lifted out of the outer trap, emptied, and placed back with minimal disturbance to the surrounding soil and vegetation. A small hole, covered with fine mesh provided drainage of rain water. After 1959, protective covers were placed over the pitfalls to avoid rain, sand and debris building up inside the traps. These were made from opaque metal sheets placed a few centimetres above the trap using pins in the soil.

The traps were placed in groups of three (hereafter referred to as a 'series'), typically set in a straight line with 10m distance between traps, with the middle trap containing a metal funnel (Fig. 1c) equipped with a container filled with 3% formaldehyde solution as killing agent. The two outer traps did not contain killing preservative and caught beetles live. The reason for using these two trap types, was because the live traps were supposedly more efficient at catching middle sized and larger species, whereas the funnel traps caught more smaller species (Den Boer 1977). Generally, the beetles trapped in the live traps were later killed and collected for identification.

We obtained the historical locations of the trap series from a range of sources, including publications Den Boer and Van Dijk 1994, reports (Van Tol 2000 Verhagen and Vermeulen 2005), historical maps and field notes from the BSW archive. The coordinates provided in the Darwin Core archive represent the locations to the best of our knowledge, pieced together from the various sources and descriptions. Their accuracy varies between 20 and 10.000m.

Each sampling year ran from March 1st until February 28 (29th) of the next year, with some variation around these dates (see Data Range). The traps were typically emptied weekly, on the same day of the week, but this was variable in winter, with occasionally longer trapping periods around the holidays. All collected specimens were identified to species level, enumerated, and in most cases separated between males and females by ground-beetle specialists working at the BSW.

Quality control: Quality control of the digitisation process involved a number of steps and was based on double entry principles (Barchard and Verenikina 2013). The aim was to achieve a <0.1% error rate.

1) The archive consists of large paper sheets on which all catches of a species were recorded per trap on each sampling date per year (see Fig. 1e), including marginal row and column sums. We used these marginal sums for comparison with the row and column sums calculated during digitisation. Any differences in marginal totals between our entries and the paper year sheets were then traced to the cell in which the error originated. Both errors in sampling date and trap number could thus be corrected.

The row and column totals on the yearsheets were almost perfectly matched with the single entries, showing the high quality of the archive. It should be noted however, that the year sheets themselves were derived from field and lab notebooks which have mostly been lost. We do, therefore, not know the accuracy of this transcription.

2) The second step was to compare the complete list of species and total capture per species that were digitised with those published by (Den Boer 1977).

3) Finally, we compared our data entry of 30 paper sheets (six sheets per year of two rare, two intermediate, and two abundant species, with a total 6326 entries) to a previous digitisation effort of these species, and checked each mismatch with the original paper sheets. This showed no errors in our data entry.

Geographic coverage

Description: Pitfalls were placed in several nature reserves in the province of Drenthe, in the north of the Netherlands. We derived the historical locations of the traps from publications (Den Boer and Van Dijk 1994, Verhagen and Vermeulen 2005), historical hand-drawn maps, and a report that was written when the biological station was discontinued in 1998 (Van Tol 2000).

Coordinates: 52.7793 and 52.8363 Latitude; 6.4017 and 6.6152 Longitude.

Taxonomic coverage

Description: All individuals belonging to the beetle family Carabidae were identified and enumerated. See for the complete list of species Table 1

Taxa included:

Rank	Scientific Name
kingdom	Animalia
phylum	Arthropoda
class	Insecta
order	Coleoptera
superfamily	Caraboidea
family	Carabidae

Temporal coverage

Data range: 1959-3-01 - 1960-2-24; 1961-2-25 - 1962-2-21; 1963-3-06 - 1964-2-26; 1965-3-03 - 1966-2-23; 1966-3-02 - 1967-2-22.

Notes: The sampling years in this dataset run from March until February of the next year. The closest sampling dates to March 1st are taken to be the start and end of the running year.

Collection data

Collection name: The paper archive of the BSW is now stored in the archive of Naturalis Biodiversity Center, Leiden the Netherlands. Originally, all samples and by-catch were stored at the BSW in Wijster. When the BSW was dissolved in 1998, part of the samples were stored at Naturalis Biodiversity Center. Of the large amount of original material, it was decided that the catch from all funnel traps was stored for every fourth year (1959 and 1963 in the present dataset). In addition, the catch from the funnel traps was stored for all years for specific locations: B, N, AY and BJ, and all material from all traps in other rare habitat types: (locations G, L, O, Y, AB, BN, BO, TA, TB, TC, TD, TE, TF. This information is available in the Humboldt extension file.

Specimen preservation method: ethanol 70%, dry voucher collection

Usage licence

Usage licence: Other

IP rights notes: CC-BY-4.0

Data resources

Data package title: Biological Station Wijster standard trapping program: Sampling event data for ground beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae) <https://www.gbif-uat.org/dataset/280d6cc5-b4d8-4c0e-adeb-9120f515a047> (45.486 occurrences). The data are published as a Darwincore archive with Humboldt extension on GBIF. The events follow four hierarchical levels: 1) at the dataset level, the information is stored that is general for the dataset 2) seriesYear contains the location information for each set of three traps for a whole running year. 3) TrapYear contains the information for that trap for the whole running year: trap type and storage of specimens. 4) trapDate contains the information of each individual sampling event. The occurrences are linked to the lowest level (4). Events during which no ground beetles were collected are present in the dataset with scientificName = Carabidae, individualCount = 0 and occurrenceStatus = 'absent'

Resource link: <https://doi.org/10.15468/3mcqja>

Alternative identifiers: https://ipt.nlbif.nl/resource?r=bsw_standard_series

Additional information

As with all datasets, there are a number of things that should be taken into consideration when using the dataset:

1) The catch from all traps was normally collected weekly, but exceptions were made in winter, where occasionally weeks were skipped, or collection days were postponed to avoid holidays. Hence, the catch accumulated until the next collection date. The catch was not collected on the following dates: 6 March 1963, 13 March 1963, 25 December 1963, 24 November 1965, 12 January 1966, 19 January 1966, 26 January 1966, 9 February 1966, 16 February 1966, 30 November 1966, 11 January 1967, 15 February 1967.

2) At present, we have a poor overview of the functionality of individual traps for each event. We know that the traps were affected by rain water running into the traps, ground water pushing the traps out of the ground, damage to the traps by livestock or humans, but because this was not systematically recorded, we have not included the sparse information that is available to us in the dataset. Previous analyses have ignored trap functionality and added up all dates and all three traps of a running year for analysis.

Thereby implicitly assuming such disturbances to be homogeneously distributed among traps and years.

3) Some taxonomically close species were not separated during identification, mostly because these pairs were not recognised as separate species at the time of identification (Den Boer pers.comm. 1999, Van Dijk pers. comm. 1999):

- *Calathus melanocephalus* / *C. cinctus* (= *C. erythroderus*)
- *Bradycellus collaris* (= *B. caucasicus*) / *B. harpalinus*
- *Pterostichus nigrita* / *P. rhaeticus*
- *Bembidion lampros* / *B. properans* (systematically identified as *B. lampros*)
- *Poecilus versicolor* (= *Pterostichus coeruleescens*) / *P. cupreus*. *P. cupreus* is currently present in the study area, but it is unclear if it was present in the historical period. This species pair was not flagged in 1999 by the original data collectors.

Taxa where additional species may have been overlooked:

- *Agonum fuliginosum* (may have been mixed with *A. gracile* and possibly other *Agonum* species).
- *Asaphidion flavipes* group
- *Amara*
- *Harpalus*

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by NLBIF grant nbif2023.008. We would like to thank all the workers of the former Biological Station Wijster for collecting, archiving and preserving the Wijster data since its inception in 1959. We also kindly thank Karien Lahaise, Silke Kossmann, Menno Hooft and Frank Loggen at Naturalis for assisting us with processing the original Wijster archive, and Rikjan Vermeulen and Henk de Vries for help with the copy of the archive.

Author contributions

RvK conceived of preserving and publishing the dataset. GMG and RvK digitised and cross-checked the data. RvK wrote the R scripts for publishing the dataset. GMG and RvK wrote the datapaper. Both authors agree with the final version of the paper.

References

- Barchard K, Verenikina Y (2013) Improving data accuracy: Selecting the best data checking technique. *Computers in Human Behavior* 29 (5): 1917-1922. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2013.02.021>

- Creuwels J, Pieterse S (2024) Checklist Dutch Species Register - Nederlands Soortenregister. Naturalis Biodiversity Center. Checklist dataset <https://doi.org/10.15468/rjdpzy>
- Den Boer PJ (1977) Dispersal power and survival - Carabids in a cultivated countryside. Miscellaneous papers of the Landbouw Hogeschool Wageningen. Veenman en zonen, Wageningen.
- Den Boer PJ (1979) The significance of dispersal power for the survival of species, with special reference to the carabids in a cultivated countryside. Fortschritte der Zoologie 25 (2/3): 79-94.
- Den Boer PJ, Van Dijk TS (1994) Carabids in a changing environment. Wageningen Agricultural University Papers 94 (6): 1-30.
- Den Boer PJ, Reddingius J (1996) Regulation and stabilization paradigms in population ecology. Chapman & Hall
- Gerrits GM, Hemerik L (2022) Occurrence data on beetles (Coleoptera) collected in Dutch coastal dunes between 1953 and 1960. Biodiversity Data Journal 10 <https://doi.org/10.3897/bdj.10.e90103>
- Hallmann CA, Zeegers T, Van Klink R, Vermeulen R, Van Wielink P, Spijkers H, Van Deijk J, Van Steenis W, Jongejans E (2019) Declining abundance of beetles, moths and caddisflies in the Netherlands. Insect Conservation and Diversity 13 (2): 127-139. <https://doi.org/10.1111/icad.12377>
- van Klink R, Bowler D, Gongalsky K, Swengel A, Gentile A, Chase J (2020) Meta-analysis reveals declines in terrestrial but increases in freshwater insect abundances. Science 368 (6489): 417-420. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aax9931>
- van Klink R, Bowler D, Gongalsky K, Shen M, Swengel S, Chase J (2023) Disproportionate declines of formerly abundant species underlie insect loss. Nature <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06861-4>
- Van Tol J (2000) Overdracht zoologische collectie Biologisch Station te Wijster. Museum Naturalis, Leiden.
- Verhagen R, Vermeulen R (2005) Loopkevers van het Mantingerveld - De effecten van habitatversnippering en maatregelen ter ontsnippering in beeld gebracht. Rapport Stichting WBBS, Loon.

Figure 1.

Overview of the pitfall trap design used through the decades (A-C), the geographic location of the study area (D) as well as an impression of the paper year sheets that make up the paper archive (E) and the material stored in the wet collection of Naturalis Biodiversity Center (F).

Figure 2.

Workflow for the full digitisation of the BSW archive. Sources of data and information (blue) lie at the basis of the available data that has been and will be digitised (green), which after extensive checks and corrections will be formatted in the Darwin Core format (red) and finally uploaded as a GBIF Darwin Core archive with Humboldt Extension (grey)

Table 1.

Species list of ground beetles caught in the Wijster Research Program in the years 1959, 1961, 1963, 1965, and 1966. Scientific names follow Dutch Species Register - Nederlands Soortenregister Creuwels and Pieterse (2024).

	scientificName	verbatimIdentification
1	<i>Abax parallelepipedus</i> (Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783)	<i>Abax ater</i> Villers
2	<i>Acupalpus flavicollis</i> (Sturm, 1825)	<i>Acupalpus flavicollis</i> St.
3	<i>Acupalpus parvulus</i> (Sturm, 1825)	<i>Acupalpus dorsalis</i> F.
4	<i>Agonum emarginatum</i> (Gyllenhal, 1827)	<i>Agonum moestum</i> Dfts.
5	<i>Agonum ericeti</i> (Panzer, 1809)	<i>Agonum ericeti</i> Panz.
6	<i>Agonum fuliginosum</i> (Panzer, 1809)	<i>Agonum fuliginosum</i> Panz.
7	<i>Agonum gracile</i> Sturm, 1824	<i>Agonum gracile</i> Gyll.
8	<i>Agonum marginatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Agonum marginatum</i> L.
9	<i>Agonum muelleri</i> (Herbst, 1784)	<i>Agonum mülleri</i> Hbst.
10	<i>Agonum munsteri</i> (Hellén, 1935)	<i>Agonum munsteri</i> Hellén
11	<i>Agonum sexpunctatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Agonum sexpunctatum</i> L.
12	<i>Agonum versutum</i> Sturm, 1824	<i>Agonum versutum</i> Gyll.
13	<i>Amara aenea</i> (De Geer, 1774)	<i>Amara aenea</i> de Geer
14	<i>Amara apricaria</i> (Paykull, 1790)	<i>Amara apricaria</i> Payk.
15	<i>Amara aulica</i> (Panzer, 1796)	<i>Amara aulica</i> Panz.
16	<i>Amara bifrons</i> (Gyllenhal, 1810)	<i>Amara bifrons</i> Gyll.
17	<i>Amara brunnea</i> (Gyllenhal, 1810)	<i>Amara brunnea</i> Gyll.
18	<i>Amara communis</i> (Panzer, 1797)	<i>Amara communis</i> Panz.
19	<i>Amara consularis</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Amara consularis</i> Dfts.
20	<i>Amara convexior</i> Stephens, 1828	<i>Amara convexior</i> Steph.
21	<i>Amara equestris</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Amara equestris</i> Dfts.
22	<i>Amara famelica</i> Zimmermann, 1832	<i>Amara famelica</i> Zimm.
23	<i>Amara familiaris</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Amara familiaris</i> Dfts.
24	<i>Amara fulva</i> (Müller, 1776)	<i>Amara fulva</i> de Geer
25	<i>Amara infima</i> (Gyllenhal, 1812)	<i>Amara infima</i> Dfts.
26	<i>Amara lunicollis</i> Schiødte, 1837	<i>Amara lunicollis</i> Schiødte

27	<i>Amara makolskii</i> Roubal, 1923	<i>Amara pseudocommunis</i>
28	<i>Amara plebeja</i> (Gyllenhal, 1810)	<i>Amara plebeja</i> Gyll.
29	<i>Amara praetermissa</i> (Sahlberg, 1827)	<i>Amara praetermissa</i> Sahlb.
30	<i>Amara quenseli</i> (Schönherr, 1806)	<i>Amara quenseli</i> Schönherr
31	<i>Amara similata</i> (Gyllenhal, 1810)	<i>Amara similata</i> Gyll.
32	<i>Amara spreta</i> Dejean, 1831	<i>Amara spreta</i> Dej.
33	<i>Amara tibialis</i> (Paykull, 1798)	<i>Amara tibialis</i> Payk.
34	<i>Anchomenus dorsalis</i> (Pontoppidan, 1763)	<i>Agonum dorsale</i> Pontopp.
35	<i>Anisodactylus binotatus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	<i>Anisodactylus binotatus</i> F.
36	<i>Asaphidion flavipes</i> (Linnaeus, 1760)	<i>Asaphidion falvipes</i> L.
37	<i>Badister bullatus</i> (Schrank, 1798)	<i>Badister bipustulatus</i> F.
38	<i>Bembidion bruxellense</i> Wesmael, 1835	<i>Bembidion rupestre</i> L.
39	<i>Bembidion doris</i> (Panzer, 1796)	<i>Bembidion doris</i> Gyll.
40	<i>Bembidion femoratum</i> Sturm, 1825	<i>Bembidion femoratum</i> St.
41	<i>Bembidion guttula</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	<i>Bembidion guttula</i> F.
42	<i>Bembidion humerale</i> Sturm, 1825	<i>Bembidion humerale</i> St.
43	<i>Bembidion lampros</i> (Herbst, 1784)	<i>Bembidion lampros</i> Hrbst.
44	<i>Bembidion minimum</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	<i>Bembidion minimum</i> F.
45	<i>Bembidion nigricorne</i> Gyllenhal, 1827	<i>Bembidion nigricorne</i> Gyll.
46	<i>Bembidion quadrimaculatum</i> (Linnaeus, 1760)	<i>Bembidion quadrimaculatu</i>
47	<i>Bembidion tetracolum</i> Say, 1823	<i>Bembidion ustulatum</i> L.
48	<i>Blethisa multipunctata</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Blethisa multipunctata</i> L.
49	<i>Bradycellus caucasicus</i> (Chaudoir, 1846)	<i>Bradycellus collaris</i> Payk.
50	<i>Bradycellus csikii</i> Laczó, 1912	<i>Bradycellus csikii</i> Laczó
51	<i>Bradycellus harpalinus</i> (Audinet-Serville, 1821)	<i>Bradycellus harpalinus</i> De
52	<i>Bradycellus ruficollis</i> (Stephens, 1828)	<i>Bradycellus similis</i> Dej.
53	<i>Brosicus cephalotes</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Brosicus cephalotes</i> L.
54	<i>Calathus ambiguus</i> (Paykull, 1790)	<i>Calathus ambiguus</i> Payk.
55	<i>Calathus erratus</i> (Sahlberg, 1827)	<i>Calathus erratus</i> Sahlb.
56	<i>Calathus fuscipes</i> (Goeze, 1777)	<i>Calathus fuscipes</i> Goeze
57	<i>Calathus melanocephalus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Calathus melanocephalus</i>

58	<i>Calathus mollis</i> (Marsham, 1802)	<i>Calathus mollis</i> Mrsh.
59	<i>Calathus rotundicollis</i> Dejean, 1828	<i>Calathus piceus</i> Marsh.
60	<i>Calodromius spilotus</i> (Illiger, 1798)	<i>Dromius quadrinotatus</i> Pa
61	<i>Carabus arcensis</i> Herbst, 1784	<i>Carabus arvensis</i> Hbst.
62	<i>Carabus cancellatus</i> Illiger, 1798	<i>Carabus cancellatus</i> Ill.
63	<i>Carabus granulatus</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Carabus granulatus</i> L.
64	<i>Carabus nemoralis</i> Müller, 1764	<i>Carabus nemoralis</i> Müll.
65	<i>Carabus nitens</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Carabus nitens</i> L.
66	<i>Carabus problematicus</i> Herbst, 1786	<i>Carabus problematicus</i> HB
67	<i>Chlaenius nigricornis</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	<i>Chlaenius nigricornis</i> F.
68	<i>Cicindela campestris</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Cicindela campestris</i> L.
69	<i>Cicindela hybrida</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Cicindela hybrida</i> L.
70	<i>Cicindela sylvatica</i> Linnaeus, 1758	<i>Cicindela sylvatica</i> L.
71	<i>Clivina fossor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Clivina fossor</i> L.
72	<i>Cymindis macularis</i> Fischer von Waldheim, 1824	<i>Cymindis macularis</i> Dej.
73	<i>Cymindis vaporariorum</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Cymindis vaporariorum</i> L.
74	<i>Dromius agilis</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	<i>Dromius agilis</i> F.
75	<i>Dromius quadrimaculatus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Dromius quadrimaculatus</i>
76	<i>Dyschirius globosus</i> (Herbst, 1784)	<i>Dyschirius globosus</i> Herb
77	<i>Dyschirius politus</i> (Dejean, 1825)	<i>Dyschirius politus</i> Dej.
78	<i>Dyschirius thoracicus</i> (Rossi, 1790)	<i>Dyschirius arenosus</i> Step
79	<i>Elaphrus cupreus</i> Duftschmid, 1812	<i>Elaphrus cupreus</i> Dfts.
80	<i>Elaphrus riparius</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Elaphrus riparius</i> L.
81	<i>Epaphius secalis</i> (Paykull, 1790)	<i>Trechus secalis</i> Payk.
82	<i>Harpalus affinis</i> (Schrank, 1781)	<i>Harpalus aeneus</i> F.
83	<i>Harpalus anxius</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Harpalus anxius</i> Dfts.
84	<i>Harpalus distinguendus</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Harpalus distinguendus</i> D
85	<i>Harpalus laevipes</i> Zetterstedt, 1828	<i>Harpalus quadripunctatus</i>
86	<i>Harpalus latus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Harpalus latus</i> L.
87	<i>Harpalus rufipalpis</i> Sturm, 1818	<i>Harpalus rufitarsis</i> Dfts.
88	<i>Harpalus rufipes</i> (De Geer, 1774)	<i>Harpalus pubescens</i> Müll

89	<i>Harpalus smaragdinus</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Harpalus smaragdinus</i> Dfts.
90	<i>Harpalus solitarius</i> Dejean, 1829	<i>Harpalus fuliginosus</i> Dfts.
91	<i>Harpalus tardus</i> (Panzer, 1796)	<i>Harpalus tardus</i> Panz.
92	<i>Leistus rufomarginatus</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Leistus rufomarginatus</i> Dfts.
93	<i>Leistus spinibarbis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	<i>Leistus spinibarbis</i> F.
94	<i>Leistus terminatus</i> (Panzer, 1793)	<i>Leistus rufescens</i> F.
95	<i>Limodromus assimilis</i> (Paykull, 1790)	<i>Agonum assimile</i> Payk.
96	<i>Limodromus krynickii</i> (Sperk, 1835)	<i>Agonum krynickii</i> Sperk.
97	<i>Loricera pilicornis</i> (Fabricius, 1775)	<i>Loricera pilicornis</i> F.
98	<i>Masoreus wetterhallii</i> (Gyllenhal, 1813)	<i>Masoreus wetterhallii</i> Gyll.
99	<i>Miscodera arctica</i> (Paykull, 1798)	<i>Miscodera arctica</i> Payk.
100	<i>Nebria brevicollis</i> (Fabricius, 1792)	<i>Nebria brevicollis</i> F.
101	<i>Nebria salina</i> Fairmaire & Laboulbène, 1854	<i>Nebria salina</i> Fairm.
102	<i>Notiophilus aestuans</i> Dejean, 1826	<i>Notiophilus pusillus</i> Waterh.
103	<i>Notiophilus aquaticus</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Notiophilus aquaticus</i> L.
104	<i>Notiophilus biguttatus</i> (Fabricius, 1779)	<i>Notiophilus biguttatus</i> F.
105	<i>Notiophilus germinyi</i> Fauvel, 1863	<i>Notiophilus germinyi</i> Fauv.
106	<i>Notiophilus palustris</i> (Duftschmid, 1812)	<i>Notiophilus palustris</i> Dfts.
107	<i>Notiophilus rufipes</i> Curtis, 1829	<i>Notiophilus rufipes</i> Curtis
108	<i>Olisthopus rotundatus</i> (Paykull, 1790)	<i>Olisthopus rotundatus</i> Payk.
109	<i>Oxypselaphus obscurus</i> (Herbst, 1784)	<i>Agonum obscurum</i> Hbst.
110	<i>Panagaeus cruxmajor</i> (Linnaeus, 1758)	<i>Panageus crux-major</i> L.
111	<i>Patrobus atrorufus</i> (Ström, 1768)	<i>Patrobus atrorufus</i> Ström
112	<i>Philorhizus melanocephalus</i> (Dejean, 1825)	<i>Dromius melanocephalus</i> Dfts.
113	<i>Platynus livens</i> (Gyllenhal, 1810)	<i>Agonum livens</i> Gyll.
114	<i>Poecilus lepidus</i> (Leske, 1785)	<i>Pterostichus lepidus</i> Leske
115	<i>Poecilus versicolor</i> (Sturm, 1824)	<i>Pterostichus coeruleus</i> Sturm
116	<i>Pterostichus anthracinus</i> (Panzer, 1795)	<i>Pterostichus anthracinus</i> Panz.
117	<i>Pterostichus diligens</i> (Sturm, 1824)	<i>Pterostichus diligens</i> Sturm
118	<i>Pterostichus melanarius</i> (Illiger, 1798)	<i>Pterostichus vulgaris</i> L.
119	<i>Pterostichus minor</i> (Gyllenhal, 1827)	<i>Pterostichus minor</i> Gyll.

120	<i>Pterostichus niger</i> (Schaller, 1783)	<i>Pterostichus niger</i> Schall.
121	<i>Pterostichus nigrita</i> (Paykull, 1790)	<i>Pterostichus nigrita</i> F.
122	<i>Pterostichus oblongopunctatus</i> (Fabricius, 1787)	<i>Pterostichus oblongopunc</i>
123	<i>Pterostichus quadrioveolatus</i> Letzner, 1852	<i>Pterostichus angustatus</i> D.
124	<i>Pterostichus strenuus</i> (Panzer, 1796)	<i>Pterostichus strenuus</i> Panz.
125	<i>Pterostichus vernalis</i> (Panzer, 1796)	<i>Pterostichus vernalis</i> Panz.
126	<i>Stenolophus mixtus</i> (Herbst, 1784)	<i>Stenolophus mixtus</i> Hbst.
127	<i>Stomis pumicatus</i> (Panzer, 1796)	<i>Stomis pumicatus</i> Panz.
128	<i>Syntomus foveatus</i> (Geoffroy, 1785)	<i>Metabletus foveatus</i> Fourc.
129	<i>Syntomus truncatellus</i> (Linnaeus, 1760)	<i>Metabletus truncatellus</i> L.
130	<i>Synuchus vivalis</i> (Illiger, 1798)	<i>Synuchus nivalis</i> Panz.
131	<i>Trechus obtusus</i> Erichson, 1837	<i>Trechus obtusus</i> Er.
132	<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i> (Schrank, 1781)	<i>Trechus quadristriatus</i> Schk.
133	<i>Trichocellus cognatus</i> (Gyllenhal, 1827)	<i>Trichocellus cognatus</i> Gyll.
134	<i>Trichocellus placidus</i> (Gyllenhal, 1827)	<i>Trichocellus placidus</i> Gyll.